

Understanding the local spatial and temporal patterns of attitudes towards immigration using Twitter data

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Summary

Recent years have seen a growing interest in public attitudes towards immigration. Data derived from social media are increasingly being used to study attitudes beyond the limits of traditional data sources. In this paper, we utilise a dataset of 800,000 immigration-related tweets posted from Great Britain between 2013 and 2022. We analyse the sentiment of these, show temporal trends in sentiment and map areas with high relative levels of both strongly positive and strongly negative tweets. We then model the association of demographic and contextual variables with areas producing high proportions of strongly positive and strongly negative sentiment towards immigration.

KEYWORDS: anti-immigration sentiment, social media, natural language processing, early career

1. Introduction

An emerging literature has started to utilise digital trace data in the study of public attitudes towards immigration. In this paper, we use data from Twitter to explore the local spatial and temporal patterns of immigration sentiment in Great Britain. We use ten years worth of immigration-related tweets to analyse trends in sentiment over this period and its sub-regional geography. Our results show increasing levels of polarisation, and find that areas with fewer younger people, lower levels of higher education, and fewer migrants are associated with higher proportions of tweets expressing strong negative sentiment towards immigration.

2. Research Context

Quantitative research into attitudes towards immigration has historically used data from representative, nation-wide surveys. This has allowed for robust estimates of public opinion comparable over time and across countries. However, data of this type are generally infrequently released and are unable to produce estimates at low levels of geographical granularity. Whilst there are issues around the unrepresentativeness of social media data (Mellon and Prosser, 2017), a growing literature is utilising these data to fill gaps in understanding where traditional data sources are less able to provide answers. Scholars have analysed tweets to understand discourse around the 2015 European Refugee Crisis (Özerim and Tolay, 2021), public opinion towards migration post the passage of anti-migrant laws (Flores, 2017) and the perceived rise in anti-migrant sentiment during the COVID-19 pandemic (Rowe *et al.*, 2021). A relatively unexplored area, however, is the use of tweet data to examine longer-term temporal trends in immigration sentiment or to analyse spatial patterns at the local level.

3. Data and Methods

Tweet data was collected using Twitter's academic application programming interface (API). A list of 23 (excluding plurals) immigration-related keywords/phrases were used to query the API to collect tweets posted from within Great Britain between 1st January 2013 – 31st December 2022. Keywords were selected based on previous research on a similar topic (Rowe *et al.*, 2021). The most common keywords found in collected tweets were "immigrant/migrant" (25% of the dataset), "refugee/asylum seeker" (20% of the dataset) and "immigration/migration" (20% of the dataset).

Only geo-tagged tweets (those where a user shares their location at time of posting) were collected from

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the API; after collection tweets were then geocoded to a local authority district (LAD). Location metadata from geo-tagged tweets were provided by the API either as a point location or a Twitter Place, a named location (usually a major town or city) associated with four coordinates that form a bounding box. We conducted a spatial join on this location metadata using LAD polygons to geocode each tweet in our dataset. Overall, around 800,000 tweets were collected and geocoded.

We used VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) (Hutto and Gilbert, 2014) to undertake sentiment analysis, specifically using the VADER package for R (Roehrick, 2020). This model was chosen as it is designed to assess the sentiment of text data from social media posts, as it considers the use of slang, acronyms, emojis and irregular use of punctuation and grammar. VADER is a lexicon and simple rule-based model that is sensitive to both polarity (positive vs negative) and intensity (strong vs weak) of sentiment in text. The model provides a compound score which is normalised between -1 (extreme negative) and +1 (extreme positive) which gives the overall sentiment value for a tweet. We then segment tweets into five categories depending on their compound score: strongly positive (>0.5), positive (0.05 to 0.5), neutral (-0.05 to 0.05), negative (-0.5 to -0.05), and strongly negative (<-0.5).

We then create two measures for each LAD: the proportion of strongly positive tweets and the proportion of strongly negative ones. We use these measures as dependent variables to fit two linear regression models. Independent variables were the same for each model and were chosen as previous research has highlighted they have an influence on attitudes towards migration. We model LAD-level migration sentiment as a function of an area's levels of younger residents, formal education, migrant population and urbanisation (Dražanová, 2022). Specifically, we use the proportion of adults under 30, the proportion of adults with degree-level education, the proportion of residents not born in the UK, and population density as our independent variables. Data for these was taken from the 2011 UK Census. We include also the count of tweets from each LAD in our model as a control.

4. Results

4.1 Temporal trend in sentiment

Overall, average sentiment for collected tweets was slightly negative with a mean compound score of -0.045 and remained relatively stable over time. This finding is similar to that of previous research, which finds a rise in negative tweets on immigration can trigger – and be offset by – an increase in positive ones, and vice-versa (Rowe *et al.*, 2020). We do find evidence, however, of rising attitude polarisation, with sentiment intensity increasing over our study period (Figure 1). The proportion of neutral tweets per month falls over time, whereas the proportion of both strongly positive and negative tweets rises.

Figure 1. Proportion of tweets each month by sentiment category: strongly positive (>0.5), positive (0.05 - 0.5), neutral (-0.05 - 0.05), negative (-0.5 - -0.05), and strongly negative (<-0.5), 1 January, 2013 – 31 December 2022

4.2 Spatial patterns of sentiment

The results of our mapping (Figure 2 and 3) reveals most areas produced a higher proportion of strongly negative tweets compared to strongly positive ones. We also find that urban areas tended to have relatively more strongly positive tweets and fewer strongly negative ones. This said, this is not the case entirely, with some rural areas exhibiting this same pattern.

Figure 2. Map with Greater London inset of the proportion of tweets categorised as strongly positive by LAD

Figure 3. Map with Greater London inset of the proportion of tweets categorised as strongly negative by LAD

4.3 Regression analysis

Results of linear regression analysis (Table 1) shows all independent variables to be significantly associated with both the proportion of strongly positive and strongly negative tweets. Areas with lower proportions of strongly positive tweets and higher proportions of strongly negative are associated with relatively fewer younger people, lower levels of degree-level educated residents and fewer residents not born in the UK. Despite the fact urban areas tend to exhibit more positive sentiment, once our other variables are controlled for, population density has a slight negative association with the proportion of strongly positive tweets.

Our regression results generally line up with what the literature says around the impact of demographic and contextual factors on attitudes towards migration. The influence of local levels of migration on attitudes is a topic of debate within the literature, with there being competing evidence for both a positive “contact” effect, and a negative “threat” effect (Schlueter and Scheepers, 2010). Our results provide evidence for the former.

	Proportion of Strong Positive Tweets	Proportion of Strong Negative Tweets
Constant	0.130*** (0.016)	0.281*** (0.018)
Aged 18-29 (% of adult residents)	0.219*** (0.049)	-0.223*** (0.056)
Level 4 Qualifications (% of adult residents)	0.056*** (0.022)	-0.062*** (0.025)
Non-UK Born (% of residents)	0.062*** (0.022)	-0.082*** (0.025)
Log Population Density (residents per square km)	-0.003** (0.001)	0.003* (0.002)
Log Number of Tweets	-0.003 (0.002)	0.005** (0.002)
n	361	361
R ²	0.19	0.19
Adjusted R ²	0.18	0.18
***p<0.01; **p<0.05; *p<0.1		

Table 1. Regression Results with coefficients and standard error in parenthesis

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have demonstrated a framework for the use of tweets to analyse temporal and spatial patterns of immigration sentiment. Our results show rising levels of attitude polarisation on the topic of immigration over our study period. Results of our regression analysis are consistent with what we would expect, given the literature on determinants of public opinion on migration. These results suggest the suitability of Twitter data to study patterns of migration attitudes, despite concerns surrounding data biases. Further work will improve upon this framework, and add additional spatial-temporal analysis to what has been presented above.

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Biographies

Matt Mason is a second year PhD student at the Geographic Data Science Lab at the University of Liverpool. His research interests are anti-immigration sentiment on social media, the geography of anti-immigration attitudes and the causal link between these and hate crimes within the UK.